

Review

Ionomer–catalyst interaction in the catalyst layer for alkaline membrane water electrolysis

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Alkaline membrane water electrolysis is gaining attention as a hydrogen production technology combining the advantages of the alkaline and proton exchange membrane water electrolysis. To fully utilize the potential of this technology, it is necessary to prepare a membrane-electrode assembly characterized by high efficiency and intensity of electrolysis. One of the vital demands to achieve this target is the establishment of a frequent triple-phase boundary. If a concentrated liquid electrolyte is used, this boundary occurrence is established due to the ionic conductivity of the electrolyte solution. In the case of a diluted liquid electrolyte, in the ideal case, demineralized water circulating through the cell, this task is accomplished by the interactions between catalyst and ionomer, fulfilling the role of binder and ion conductor. This review focuses on advances in the second approach, namely ionomer design, catalyst layer composition, and the impact of the selected parameters such as catalyst to binder ratio, catalyst load, and type of membrane-electrode assembly.

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Introduction

In an alkaline membrane water electrolysis cell (AMWE, membrane here means anion-selective membrane), polymer binders — also referred to as ionomers —

represent an essential component of the membrane electrode assembly (MEA). Their primary functions are first to enable ionic conduction within the catalyst layer (CL) by facilitating the hydroxide ion transport to or from active catalytic sites [1,2]. In the second place, they provide CL mechanical cohesion by binding catalyst particles between themselves and to the substrate surface. The binder allows the formation of a stable, interconnected microstructure of the CL with appropriate porosity, water distribution, and gas transport, that is, factors critical for MEA efficiency and durability [3,4].

There are two main strategies for incorporating binders in MEA fabrication: catalyst-coated membrane (CCM) and catalyst-coated substrate (CCS). In the CCM approach, CLs are applied directly on the surface of the membrane, maximizing the ionic contact between these two components [5]. In the CCS method, the CL is first deposited on a porous electron-conductive support and later assembled with the membrane. This approach offers more flexibility in fabrication and continuous electron contact for catalyst particles. However, at the same time, it may introduce additional resistance at the interface with the polymer membrane.

While membranes and binders may share similar ionic functionalities, they have different roles and have to satisfy different mechanical requirements. Both components must provide long-term dimensional and chemical stability. On the other hand, binders must be processable, adequately adhere to catalysts, and resist to the mechanical tension caused by the evolved gas phase. Because of these differing demands and different approaches to MEA (CCM or CCS), it is common — and often beneficial — for the binder material to differ from the membrane material in properties.

The second part of the CL represents the catalyst. Both parts, the ionomer and catalyst, must correspondingly interact to form a well-performing CL. The deposition of the CL represents a complex task influenced by several parameters. As the main ones, along with materials selection, the ratio between catalyst and ionomer load shall be mentioned. It influences the performance of the CL due to the tuning of the ratio between electronic and ionic conductivity, as well as mechanical stability. Another parameter represents the total catalyst

load, which is related to the thickness of the CL, as well as the mass and the charge transport constraints. Significant differences can be found between catalysts based on platinum group metals (PGM; Pt, Ir, Ru, Pd) and non-platinum group metals (PGM-free; like Ni, Co, Fe, Mn, Mo, Cu).

The aim of this paper is therefore to critically review current knowledge on the research and development of the AMWE CL. This includes information on the types of commercially available ionomers as well as trends in the development of the new materials. In the next part, the impact of the ionomer interaction with the catalyst is discussed with a special focus on the catalyst-to-binder ratio (CBR), total catalyst load, and MEA type.

Catalyst-ionomer interactions

The CL consists of a mixture of catalyst particles and an anion-selective ionomer that facilitates hydroxide ion transport and maintains structural cohesion. In CCM configuration, the ionomer must also ensure intimate contact between the CL and the membrane, directly influencing ionic connectivity and interfacial resistance [5,6]. On the anode side, where oxygen evolution reaction occurs under alkaline and oxidizing conditions, the ionomer is particularly vulnerable to degradation [7,8].

The functional interface between the catalyst and the ionomer plays a central role in determining both the performance and durability of AMWE. This interface is governed by a combination of electrostatic, chemical, and morphological interactions. Electrostatic interactions arise from the charge of the fixed cationic groups of the ionomer (quaternary ammonium, piperidinium, imidazolium, etc.) and the charged catalyst surfaces, affecting polymer distribution and adhesion. Their strength depends on catalyst composition, surface chemistry, and hydration state, as shown for Ni-based anodes and carbon-supported cathodes [6]. Chemical interactions include hydrogen bonding and donor-acceptor interactions between surface functional groups and polymer moieties, which can enhance ionomer anchoring and reduce delamination [5,7].

Morphological interactions involve how the ionomer physically distributes around catalyst particles, influenced by its microstructure, porosity, and processing. Several studies have demonstrated that tailoring binder porosity improves water management and OH⁻ access within the CL, enhancing triple-phase boundary coverage and in-cell performance [5,8].

Ultimately, the effectiveness of the CL depends on how these interactions are engineered during fabrication. Ink composition, casting protocols, and drying methods determine how well the ionomer wets the catalyst, forms

percolating ionic networks, and resists degradation. As emphasized in recent works, rational tuning of ionomer chemistry, processing, and interfacial morphology is essential to advance durable, high-performance AMWE systems [5–8].

The durability of catalyst-ionomer interactions is a central factor influencing long-term CL performance in AMWEs. Chemical degradation primarily affects the ionomer phase, especially at the anode, where the oxygen evolution reaction induces highly oxidative conditions. The chemical degradation of the ionomer is usually much harsher than that of the membrane [9]. This leads to the decomposition of cationic groups, backbone cleavage, and eventual loss of ion-exchange capacity [5,10].

Mechanical degradation includes delamination, cracking, and particle detachment due to gas evolution, differential swelling, and dissolution of the ionomer. These processes disrupt the triple-phase boundary and impair catalyst utilization, especially under dry-wet cycling or pressurized operation [5]. In their study, Rossini et al. demonstrated that ionomer chemistry and content significantly influence both adhesion and degradation rates. Low ion exchange capacity ionomers and hydrophobic binders like Nafion™ improved the mechanical and chemical stability of the anode CL, despite moderate initial performance [11].

Given that the chemical and mechanical stability of the catalyst-ionomer interface is closely tied to polymer structure, the choice of ionomeric polymer is of high importance for both initial performance and long-term durability in AMWE CLs. No general rules directing this selection exist, and each case requires, up to now, more or less empirical optimization.

Commercial ionomers

The common practice is the usage of ionomer and membrane materials from the same chemical family to optimize MEA integrity and electrochemical performance. For example, the FAA-3 ionomer is commonly paired with the FAA3-50® membrane, both produced by Fuma-Tech [12–16]. Similarly, the AS-4 ionomer is used with the A201 membrane, both from Tokuyama. In the case of PiperION, both the ionomer and membrane are derived from poly(aryl piperidinium) structures, offering improved compatibility and performance in harsh alkaline environments.

As classified in Table S2, commercial polymer binders used in AMWE can be categorized based on their ionic functionality into three main types: (i) anion-conductive (ionomeric) binders, (ii) inert binders, and (iii) mixed anion- and cation-conductive binders.

The main group represents an anion-selective ionomer with quaternary ammonium, piperidinium, or

imidazolium moieties, which are responsible for hydroxide ion conduction within the CL. As main commercial representatives, FAA-3, PiperION, Sustanion, and Aemion can be mentioned. The presence of functional groups is essential for establishing effective triple-phase boundaries and ensuring continuous ionic pathways between the membrane and catalyst sites in an environment of low ionic conductivity.

As an inert binder, polytetrafluoroethylene is applied, which is mainly used to enhance mechanical and chemical stability, thus providing critical mechanical support and improving CL structural stability. They are particularly useful in CCS-type MEAs and in environments where ionic conductivity is secured by a liquid electrolyte [17].

Finally, the third group of mixed-functionality binders integrates both anion- and cation-conductive components. These hybrid systems aim to improve polymer binder cohesion and overall MEA durability.

As visualized in Scheme 1, the chemical architecture of ionomers continues to evolve toward nonfluorinated, fully aromatic hydrocarbon backbones and cyclic cations integrated directly into the backbone. These designs eliminate vulnerable sites like ether and benzylic linkages, which are susceptible to nucleophilic attack under alkaline conditions. Most of the high-performance anion-selective ionomers are based on nonfluorinated, fully aromatic hydrocarbon backbones, particularly polymers such as poly(phenylene oxide) (PPO), poly(arylene ether), and more advanced poly(phenylene) or poly(aryl piperidinium) architectures. These structures offer enhanced thermal and chemical stability compared to older designs containing ether or benzylic linkages [9,18]. The

fully aromatic backbone is a crucial advancement in ionomer design. For instance, commercially available PAP-TP-85 and PiperION use poly(aryl piperidinium) structures in which the cationic piperidinium groups are tethered directly within the backbone. This configuration not only improves mechanical robustness and ionic conductivity but also substantially extends the operational lifetime in concentrated KOH solutions at elevated temperatures [19,20]. In contrast, earlier-generation ionomers like FAA-3 or Aemion use side-chain tethered quaternary ammonium (NR_3^+) groups, which, while functional, are more susceptible to Hofmann elimination or nucleophilic substitution over time [12,15,16,21].

The cationic groups embedded in commercially available anion-selective materials also impact stability and conductivity. Piperidinium groups have become prominent because of their cyclic, sterically protected structures, which offer better alkaline tolerance than traditional linear quaternary ammonium groups. Similarly, multi-quaternized variants such as PAP-TP-85-MQN demonstrate higher IECs and superior ionic conductivity due to increased density of fixed cationic sites [20].

Structural trends in non-commercial ionomers for AMWE

The growing complexity and performance demand of AMWE systems have catalyzed the development of innovative polymer ionomers. In contrast to commercially available ones, these research-grade polymers allow for precise tuning of structural and functional properties and are typically paired with experimental membranes in custom MEA configurations. The current key design

Scheme 1

Evolution of commercial ionomer structures.

trend in ionomer structure is similar to commercial ionomers and involves the use of fully aromatic, ether-free backbones that resist alkaline degradation and offer stable ionic pathways [22]. Although limited, recent research on non-commercial [8,23–26] binders allows us to distinguish several key strategies aimed explicitly at enhancing ionomer durability and stability, including the use of cross-linked polymers [25,26], enhancing chemical robustness and mechanical strength by forming stable three-dimensional networks. Another approach involves composite ionomer systems, where multiple functional materials are combined to achieve synergistic performance benefits [4,8]. Additionally, block copolymers are synthesized to promote improved ionic transport and controlled phase morphology, optimizing conductivity and structural integrity [8,23,24]. Finally, spacer-based designs are employed to introduce steric hindrance or flexible molecular segments, helping to mitigate degradation and extend operational stability [27,28].

Among various strategies, the use of composite ionomers has gained attention for improving the performance and durability of AMWEs. Choosing different polymers as co-binders can strengthen interfacial adhesion or

optimize transport properties. In a recent study by Hyun et al. [4], the issue of early-stage performance degradation — caused by catalyst detachment and delamination of the CL — was addressed by introducing Nafion as a co-binder (Figure 1a). This approach mitigated the delamination and improved the mechanical integrity of the CL, ultimately leading to enhanced operational stability and performance. The composite binder strategy can also be applied to balance ion conductivity and gas permeability. By blending SEBS-DABCO, an ion-conducting polymer, with PIM-1, a microporous polymer (Figure 1b), enhanced water and gas transport properties can be achieved while maintaining structural integrity [8].

Block copolymers offer a structural approach to enhance ionomer performance by enabling microphase separation, which creates distinct hydrophilic and hydrophobic domains. This morphology supports efficient ion transport while maintaining mechanical and chemical stability. While attempts are made to develop ionomers based on methacrylate monomers (Figure 1c), which demonstrate good current density performances and promising stability [29], the most typical structure is represented by poly(vinylbenzyl) blocks bearing cationic groups as

Figure 1

Representative structures of non-commercial polymer binders AMWE. Composite materials – quaternized poly(carbazole)-based polymer with Nafion (a) [4], SEBS-DABCO with PIM (b) [8], Block copolymers – [4]; quaternized Poly(DMAEMA-co-TFEMA-co-BMA) (c) [29]; Piperidine-based polymers – poly(terphenyl piperidinium) containing hydrophilic crown ether units (d) [27], triblock copolymer incorporating N-methylpiperidinium and hydrophobic segments (e) [28]; Cross-linked polymers (f,g): quaternary ammonium grafted poly(vinyl benzyl chloride) based ionomer (f) [26], cross-linking of poly(norbornene) (g) [25].

the ion-conductive phase, while hydrophobic blocks like polyethylene (PE) control water uptake and limit excessive swelling. The length of the tuning block — particularly the PE content — can balance conductivity with durability. Importantly, localizing water and hydroxide ions to the side chains minimizes contact with vulnerable aryl-ether backbones, thus mitigating degradation via nucleophilic attack. This structural strategy enables the design of ionomers with a tailored conductivity and enhanced alkaline stability [28].

Another trend in ionomer design involves tailoring the polymer backbone via inserting spacer structures to optimize both stability and ion transport (Figure 1d,e). For example, Lim et al. employ alkyl spacers to enhance flexibility and ionic mobility [22]. Alternatively, recent work has explored the use of crown ether-like moieties as internal spacers, integrated alongside cyclic N,N-dimethylpiperidinium (DMP) cations in the polymer backbone. This architecture enhances water uptake and promotes efficient ion-dipole interactions, facilitating improved hydroxide ion transport [27].

To conclude this chapter, both the commercial and innovative binders often originate from similar polymer classes — such as poly(phenylene oxide), polyaromatic hydrocarbons, and block copolymers — and face common challenges like alkaline degradation. Innovative variants under development, however, adopt experimental architectures like functional groups with conformation protecting them from Hofmann elimination reaction, or polymer backbone chains allowing for the phase separation and domain microstructure formation. Such materials, often with tunable compositions, can achieve improved properties due to structure–property relationships.

Catalyst layers in AMWE

This section focuses on the interactions of the catalyst and polymer binder in the CL. Unfortunately, the interactions between catalyst particles and the polymer binder in MEAs have been studied so far mainly from the mechanical stability point of view. These interactions can, due to the difference in charge of the functional group and electrode itself, result in attraction or repulsion effects between the catalyst and polymer binder, respectively [30]. More research is needed to provide detailed insight into these specific interactions.

From PGM catalysts, IrO₂ and Pt are commonly applied to the anode and cathode, respectively [13,14,31]. However, because of the cost, PGM-free catalysts represent the preferred option. Transition metal oxides, phosphides, and alloys, such as NiFe₂O₄, NiCo₂O₄, NiMoO₄, CoFeO_x, CoO_x, Cu_xCo_xO_x, or NiCoP, represent an especially promising option for alkaline water electrolysis [15,24,26,30,32–34].

Effect of catalyst-to-binder ratio on catalyst binder interactions

To identify the most promising trends in the CBR parameter for both CCM- and CCS-MEA, the literature data of current densities achieved at a cell voltage of 2 V were gathered for different CBRs and plotted in Figure 2a. As expected, the data reported in the literature were obtained under different conditions (KOH concentrations, temperatures, etc.), which limits the possibility of direct comparison.

As Figure 2a shows, quite a wide range of CBRs from 40 to 97 wt% of catalysts were used. The best performances are typically achieved around 90 wt% of the catalyst in the CL for PGM catalysts and in the range 70–90 wt%

Figure 2

(a) Effect of CBR on current density at 2 V and (b) effect of catalyst load. Orange circle: PGM catalysts; Blue square: PGM-free catalysts.

for PGM-free catalysts. The optimum range for CBR is given by the number of triple-phase boundaries established within CL.

The catalyst content of 10 wt% and lower was proposed as optimal by several authors investigating in detail the effect of CBR [14,24,35]. Limited electron conductivity [24,35] and/or mass transport limitations [14,35] were observed as limiting parameters with catalyst content above 10 wt%. Limited electron conductivity was attributed to the strong adhesion of the polymer binder to the catalyst. In such a case, the catalyst particles are encapsulated by the electrically non-conductive polymer, resulting in a thin active area of CL [24]. Mass transport limitation issues can be caused by different reasons, such as ionomer-dominated areas formation [14] or a decrease in the porosity of CL [35].

Despite the fact that the above-mentioned works showed similar optimal CBR values, this cannot be defined generally, as it depends on the specific interactions between ionomer and catalyst. One of the parameters represents a backbone polymer. The abovementioned works, identifying low polymer binder content as beneficial [14,24,35], utilized the nonfluorinated fully carbon-based backbones. On the other hand, applying the fluorinated alternatives resulted in optimal CBRs 80/20 [30] or 75/25 [31]. However, in work [31], different CBRs of 75/25 and 95/5 were used for the cathode and anode, respectively.

Another motivation for optimizing polymer binder content can represent improved long-term stability. The degradation may include an increase in i) charge transfer resistance and ii) ohmic resistance of MEA. The first case is caused by the catalyst activity loss, catalyst particles detachment from CL, or loss of the interface between polymer binder and catalyst [31,36]. The increase in ohmic resistance shows anion-selective membrane (ASM) or polymer binder degradation, causing loss of its ionic conductivity and reduction of the three-phase contact occurrence [36]. However, it is generally difficult to identify the reason for the voltage/current change without specialized techniques like electrochemical impedance spectroscopy or post-mortem analysis of the MEA. Most of the post-mortem MEA testing did not show any or only minor signs of ASM or catalyst particles degradation [4,15,23,31]. On the other hand, delamination of the CL from the membrane or loss of the catalyst particles was observed [14].

It follows from the above review that the prevailing number of studies utilizes ionomer loading of 10 wt% and lower. This appears to be connected with the undesired interaction of the ionomer with the catalyst, especially encapsulation of the catalyst particles by polymer phase, deteriorating thus electron contact in the

CL [24] and product removal [35]. In selected cases, it was found preferable to use different ionomer loading on the anode and cathode side of the cell, which underlines the specificity of interaction of ionomer with catalyst [31]. The binding ability of the anion-selective polymer binder can also influence the degradation rate [4], but it seems that the main stability issue is not connected with the polymer binder degradation.

Effect of catalyst loading

In the traditional understanding, higher catalyst loading provides more active sites, thus accelerating the electrode reaction rate. On the other hand, it increases the thickness of the CL. This can have two negative consequences. Firstly, a higher CL thickness means potentially higher ohmic resistance. For example, this was observed by Kreider et al. [37], who used catalysts with low conductivity (NiFe_2O_4 and Co_3O_4) and observed a minimum effect of increasing loading on the MEA performance.

Secondly, in the case of electrical and ionic conductivities of the CL high enough, the reaction takes place predominantly at the CL and polymer membrane interface, as it follows from the porous electrode theory. The produced gaseous phase thus must penetrate through the entire thickness of the CL. If it is too high, the pressure of the gaseous phase at the interface will increase, resulting potentially in CL delamination. Even if the delamination does not occur, an increase in the pressure of the gaseous phase close to the ASM will increase gas crossover.

The loading depends on the type of catalyst. According to data reported in the literature, the loading of PGM catalysts is almost exclusively below 5 cm^{-2} with an optimum of approximately $2 \text{ mg Ir black cm}^{-2}$ [35]. The loading of the PGM-free catalyst can achieve up to 20 cm^{-2} [38] (see Figure 2b). As visible from Figure 2b, increasing the catalyst amount in the CL above 5 cm^{-2} does not have a positive effect on electrolysis performance. This is in agreement with the discussion of the CL thickness.

Effect of the catalyst layer substrate

Although CCM is commonly used for PEM fuel cells and water electrolyzers, such an approach is not yet well-established in AMWE. This is due to several reasons. Firstly, anion-selective polymer binders that are stable and efficient under AMWE conditions are still under development. Another reason consists of the deposition methods of the CL, including often a high-temperature step, which may lead to degradation of the ASM, for example, hot-pressing. The CCM technique is investigated because of the improved ionic contact between catalyst powder and polymer binder (ion conductor), which makes it possible for a diluted KOH

Figure 3

Comparison of current densities achieved with CCM- and CCS-MEA.

solution or even pure water to be used as a circulating electrolyte.

As shown in Figure 3, the current densities achieved by both types of MEA are comparable to or slightly higher than CCM-MEAs. However, CCM-MEAs achieved high current densities mostly using PGM catalysts having typically better catalytic properties (see Figure 3). This appears to be caused primarily by the lower electronic conductivity of the PGM-free catalysts. For low-conductivity catalysts, the substrate used at CCS provides a better electronic contact and charge distribution.

Conclusion

This short review confirms that, despite significant advances in the field of alkaline polymer electrolyte membranes recently, the development of ionomers serving as binders in CL is still an open field of research. This is mainly because interaction between the catalyst and binder is, despite its high importance, still only poorly understood. The trends currently followed may be summarized as the improvement of both the ionomer and ionomer/catalyst alkaline and oxidative stability, where, for ionomers, the backbone structures move to ether-free fully aromatic polymers, and the better interaction with the catalyst is usually achieved by the introduction of an additional neutral or oppositely charged polymer. Structures with stable cyclic cations tethered directly inside the backbone or separated by linkers can also be distinguished as future perspectives that will allow control of water uptake and conductivity of the ionomers. However, a relatively low number of published studies and a lack of standardization in developed ionomer testing prevent a more detailed analysis and broader conclusions. Yet, it may be stated that intensive

research in the field of new ionomers satisfying significant demands, as well as CL engineering, will be a crucial prerequisite to allow the design of the new generation AMWE cell.

Data Availability

No data were used for the research described in the article.

Declaration of Competing Interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Supporting information

Supplementary data associated with this article can be found in the online version at [doi:10.1016/j.coche.2025.101220](https://doi.org/10.1016/j.coche.2025.101220).

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